

Untangling the relationships between SARS-CoV-2 related coronaviruses

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Abstract

When SARS-CoV-2 broke out there were just two published sequences from its clade, despite 15 years of intensive sampling for bat coronaviruses. While sharing some distinguishing features, these viruses (ZC45/ZXC21) published by a group of PLA epidemiologists in March 2018, were too evolutionarily distant to be direct precursors. On January 20th, 2020, with the outbreak out of control, Chinese authorities belatedly acknowledged the virus could transmit between humans. Only then were more sequences published, though it is clear these had been known much earlier. As debate raged over a possible artificial origin, more sequences were published conveniently addressing specific points of contention. The provenance of many of these are questionable. Most groups (even foreign) publishing SARS-CoV-2 related sequences have close links to China’s military and/or WIV, although this isn’t always disclosed or obvious. This analysis of evolutionary dynamics highlights inconsistencies between sequences that are difficult to explain using a conventional model of viral evolution. Some scientists have proposed a unique “mosaic” evolution, driven by exceptionally frequent recombination. However, this is still insufficient to explain all anomalies. Another possibility that must be considered is that there has been an extensive effort to “inhibit attribution”. This likely involved the fabrication of sequence data and/or deliberate contamination of samples with synthetic RNA. Concerningly there is evidence these efforts began even before the outbreak, implying premeditation.

Introduction

Rationale

This paper uses analysis of the ratios of synonymous to non-synonymous mutations in an effort to detect if sequence data may have been fabricated. The reasoning is that if someone wanted to fabricate sequence data or create synthetic RNA to create a false evolutionary trail, it is straightforward to add synonymous (or silent) mutations to create the impression of genetic distance by lowering the nucleotide identity. Adding non-synonymous mutations is risky in that there is the possibility of creating a non-functional protein domain, or non-viable protein or organism.

Provenance of sequences relevant to SARS-CoV-2 origin

		SADS	ZC45 /ZXC21	RaTG13	ZC45L GD	Pangolin GD	Pangolin GX	RmYN02	RacCS203 (Thailand)	Rc-o319 (Japan)	RshTT182 (Cambodia)	PDF-2370 (Uganda)	Banals (Laos)	BFSV02 YN	RV/N21-29 (Vietnam)	CN Wildlife
		Aug-17	Mar-18	Jul-18*	Jul-18*	Sep-19*	Feb-20	Apr-20	Nov-20	Dec-20	Jan-21	Apr-21	Aug-21	Dec-22	Sep-23	Sep-23
WIV	Zhengli Shi, Peng Zhou	✓		✓	✓		✓									
PLA AMMS	Wuchun Cao, Yigang Tong, Changchu	✓			✓	✓		✓								✓
PLA JLSF	Changchun Wang		✓													
Guangzhou Zoo	Chen Wu					✓										✓
U Shandong	Weifeng Shi	✓						✓								
SCAU	Yongyi Shen, Jing-Yun Ma	✓				✓										✓
CAMS	Yuhai Bi	✓						✓								
IPS, others	Gary Wong, Jie Cui	✓			✓											
GIABR		✓				✓										
HKU	Tommy Lam, Guan Yi					✓	✓									✓
USYD	Edward Holmes			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓						✓		
PREDICT	Jonna Mazet, Christine Johnson									✓	✓					
NUS	Linfu Wang	✓							✓							
Institut Pasteur	M. Eloit, S. Temmam, E. Simon-Loriere									✓		✓			✓	
U Tokyo	Shin Murakami, Yoshihiro Kawaoka									✓						
EcoHealth	Peter Daszak	✓														
U Sun Yat-Sen														✓		

SADS

In late 2017 several Chinese groups reported outbreaks of a new coronavirus infecting pigs that led to often fatal diarrhea. This disease was found to be closely related to a previously known bat alphacoronavirus, HKU2. Although this virus is unrelated to SARS or SARS-CoV-2, and isn't known to have infected humans, it is included in this study because:

- The work links individuals and institutions who subsequently work on SARS-CoV-2 origins, including military (AMMS), state institutions (WIV/CAMS/China CDC), universities (SCAU, GIABR, Shandong) and foreign collaborators.
- It purports to show a zoonosis of a coronavirus directly between bats and livestock, with subsequent transmission between pigs, and the potential for onward transmission to humans.

- Timing.

The author list on the SADS paper¹ includes the senior authors on several SARS-CoV-2 related papers: Zhengli Shi (RaTG13), Yigang Tong (GX pangolin), Linfa Wang (RacCS203), Weifeng Shi (RmYN02) and many other authors from AMMS, WIV, Shandong University, GIABR and SCAU. Another paper was published at around the same time speculating that pigs might (in future) be an intermediate species in a bat to human coronavirus zoonosis. The authors of this paper include China CDC head George Gao, Gary Wong (Institut Pasteur Shanghai), and Yuhai Bi (of CAS Microbiology an author on the RmYN02 paper).

Zhoushan viruses (ZC45/ZXC21)

ZC45 and ZXC21 were the first full-length SARS-CoV-2 related viruses to be published², and the only ones in the public domain prior to the outbreak (many more RdRp-only sequences were published by the same authors). The authors are mostly PLA, from the Third Military Medical University, Chongqing, and the Research Institute for Medicine of Nanjing Command. Senior author Changjun Wang has been linked to the Joint Logistics Support Force (JLSF), a recently established arm of the PLA that figured prominently in the pandemic response in China.

Sequences were published on GenBank on March 28, 2018. The group successfully infected suckling BALB/c mice by intracranial inoculation using tissue from infected bats. However, the Zoushan viruses have RBD deletions that make them unlikely to bind ACE2 or transmit via the respiratory system. Nonetheless they share distinctive characteristics with SARS-CoV-2 (such as the Envelope gene) that were unseen before.

Authors noted that at 81% similarity to SARS, these were more distant than other known bat sarbecovs like Rp3. However some scientists had expressed interest in finding viruses that were approximately 20% different to SARS (notably a Sino-US consortium including WIV and UNC's Ralph Baric, who had submitted a research proposal known as DEFUSE³).

Early in the outbreak, ZC45 and ZXC2 were discussed as closest to SARS-CoV-2⁴, at 89.1% nucleotide identity. This was due to the suppression of other sequence data, such as RaTG13, which is much closer at 96.2%. WIV also has 4 sequences closely related to ZC45 (>99% identity in the spike), purportedly collected in Guangdong and uploaded to GenBank in 2018. These were never disclosed and remain suppressed on GenBank, but can be downloaded with the accession. These are Rs8561, Rs8572, Rs8586, Rp140346 (accessions: MH615970, MH615971, MH615972, MH615973). The spike sequences of Rs8561/Rs8572/Rs8586 are identical, while the corresponding ORF8 and RdRp sequences contain minor differences.

There are ~160 suppressed sequences in total which can be downloaded using accession numbers in the range MH615839:MH615992

Jones et al, discovered reads from a novel virus that is related to both ZC45 and the GX pangolin in different parts of the genome⁵. The reads were extracted from metagenomic data uploaded by a group that includes Edward Holmes and AMMS authors including Changchun Tu⁶. Jones et al also found reads from cloning vectors, suggesting engineering.

RaTG13

RaTG13 was for some time, and by some evolutionary distance, the closest known sequence to SARS-CoV-2.

While the ORF8 and RdRp were sequenced and uploaded (though not published) in July 2018, the Spike and full genome weren't available until Jan 24th, 2020 on GISAID, and Jan 29th 2020 on GenBank. It is thought the full genome was sequenced some time in 2018, and certainly before June 2019 when a masters thesis was submitted describing it⁷, but not revealing the sequence.

WIV director Shi Zhengli co-authored two papers which were submitted to publishers on the same day - January 20th 2020. One of these identified ZC45 as the closest sequence to SARS-CoV-2, and made no mention of RaTG13⁸, while the other announced RaTG13 as the new closest relative⁹. Shi has not explained why she delayed announcement of this sequence, though it is clear from media interviews that she knew of its significance no later than 1st January, 2020¹⁰.

Pangolin coronaviruses

The provenance of pangolin coronaviruses have been another source of confusion.

The first paper reporting a pangolin coronavirus was submitted for publication 30 September 2019¹¹. Just three authors are named, two are from Guangdong Institute of Applied Biological Resources (GIABR). A third author, Wu Chen, is from Guangzhou Zoo. Media reports identify him as a senior veterinarian, or as the Research Director of the Guangzhou Wildlife Research Center (this is distinct from the Guangdong Wildlife Rescue Center, that housed the pangolins from Guangdong Customs in March 2019).

It is unclear who performed much of the work. Although sequencing was said to have been outsourced commercially, no-one is credited with sample preparation and virus isolation. In November 2021, a correction to a different paper suggests Wu Chen supplied metagenomic data and no samples were handled by GIABR.

The paper was published on 24th October, 2019. A GenBank BioProject (PRJNA573298) was registered on 20th September, 2019 and metadata entered. But importantly *no sequence data was released until four months later*, 22nd January, 2020.

In contrast, a later SCAU paper is much better resourced listing 25 authors, 10 of whom were involved in virus isolation and sequencing¹². The source of their data caused considerable confusion. A pre-print by Alina Chan¹³ questioned if the same data was used in both (and other) studies. A correction issued by SCAU *17 months after publication*, and 12 months after Chan's query, clarified that much of the data was the same as that used in the GIABR paper¹⁴. SCAU supplemented that with additional data obtained by sequencing other pangolin samples (also via Wu Chen).

The SCAU publication was preceded by a press conference on Feb 7th, 2020 with AMMS director Yang Ruifu and Wu Chen¹⁵. Media reports suggest Yang was involved in the work, although he isn't credited on the paper. The SCAU paper speculates that SARS-CoV-2 may have originated from the recombination of a pangolin coronavirus (particularly the RBD), with a bat virus similar to RaTG13. [A variation on this - that SARS-CoV-2 was the result of an artificial recombination, a chimera of RaTG13 and a pangolin](#)

[coronavirus](#) - [was proposed by “lab leakers”¹⁶](#), [and](#) also [recognized as a possibility](#) by officers from the US Defense Intelligence Agency¹⁷.

Another pangolin coronavirus paper is a collaboration between the HKU-based State Key Laboratory for Emerging Infectious Disease, the AMMS and Edward Holmes¹⁸, among others. Tong Yigang (then of AMMS) claimed to have isolated a pangolin coronavirus as early as 2017¹⁹, reportedly from frozen pangolin samples from Guanxi Customs from pangolins seized during anti-smuggling operations. This collaboration also used data on pangolins seized in Guangdong. This came via Guangzhou Customs Technology Center, who re-examined frozen samples from pangolins they seized in March, 2019 (presumably this is from the same group of pangolins as Wu Chen’s samples). Surprisingly, the only sample with coronavirus reads was a pangolin scale. The authors suggest it may have been contamination from other tissue.

Guangdong (GD) and Guanxi (GX) pangolin coronaviruses form two distinct clades of closely related variants. GD clade has an RBD that closely resembles SARS-CoV-2, with just one amino acid difference. Sequence differences within each clade aren’t material for the purposes of this study.

After the SCAU results were announced, Edward Holmes emailed the SCAU group to enquire if they had found a pangolin coronavirus that had SARS-CoV-2’s furin cleavage site (FCS) insert. This was of particular interest for many scientists (including Holmes) concerned about an artificial origin of the virus. Interestingly, the metagenomic data uploaded by AMMS for the scale sample contains a single raw read of 49 nucleotides which includes the FCS²⁰. This would likely be ignored by most sequence assembly software using default settings, so perhaps this is why it went unremarked. It is possibly contamination, but still interesting given the circumstances.

RmYn02

This sequence purportedly came from a sample collected in early 2019, by UK scientist Alice Hughes, who worked at the Xishuangbanna nature reserve in Yunnan. Hughes has stated she started collaborating with CAS Institute of Microbiology, and Shi Weifeng of Shandong University in late 2018. Hughes sent samples to Shi Weifeng for sequencing, and wasn’t involved in the process beyond that. In late January 2020, she was told Shi’s team had sequenced SARS-like coronaviruses. Shi Weifeng and his team have a close working relationship with AMMS, particularly Tong Yigang, with whom Shi jointly led China’s mission to Sierra Leone during the 2014-15 Ebola epidemic.

RmYn02 garnered particular interest due to its S1|S2 junction having some residues in common with the SARS-CoV-2’s FCS²¹. While not comprising an FCS, some have argued it suggests an evolutionary pathway. The paper claimed that it was evidence insertions could naturally occur at the S1|S2 junction, though it appears more likely to have resulted from a deletion.

Cambodian bat coronaviruses

Thai bat coronaviruses

A collaboration between a team of Thai researchers from Chulalongkorn University, and Linfa Wang’s group at Duke-NUS claim to have sequenced a SARS2r-CoV closely related to RmYN02, with similar S1|S2 junction and RBM sequence²². The senior authors include Changchung Tu from AMMS, and

Martha Stokes, the Singapore-based head of the Asian arm of DTRA’s Biological Threat Reduction Program.

Interestingly, the authors noted that RacCS203 has a distinctive ORF10, identical to ZXC21, a virus discovered over 3000km distant. This is only evident if the nucleotide sequence is translated in a different frame to that used to generate the protein sequence for ZXC21 in GenBank.

Laotian “BANAL” coronaviruses

The BANAL viruses were collected in July 2020, as the outcome of a field trip to four sites in Laos led by Institut Pasteur du Laos (IPL)²³. The expedition was proposed to be conducted with Institut Pasteur Shanghai (IPS), Pasteur’s joint venture with CAS/WIV, however it’s unclear if IPS were involved as none of their scientists are listed as authors.

In 2017, IPL conducted an expedition to these same cave systems, and collected over 500 samples from bats. Institut Pasteur’s Marc Eloit confirmed that they hadn’t sequenced any of the earlier samples, but didn’t explain why they hadn’t done this before launching a new field trip.

There are five full genome sequences published, all sarbecovs were collected from a single site, although four sites were sampled. No SARS-1 related viruses were identified. Between them they provide support for both clades of pangolin coronaviruses, RmYN02, and the “mosaic evolution” of sarbecovs via recombination. BANAL-52 supplanted RaTG13 as the closest known relative of SARS-CoV-2, removing the need for a recombination between a bat and a pangolin coronavirus. An intimation is that this one cave might contain all the “building blocks” for SARS-CoV-2, including viruses with the RmYN02-like proto-FCS (i.e. BANAL-116, BANAL-247). This is analogous to WIV’s claim to have found all the building blocks for SARS-1 in a single cave in Yunnan, speculating that they are constantly recombining, despite not having found the direct ancestor to SARS²⁴.

Recently it became known that Institut Pasteur had returned to the site in 2021 and sequenced a further related virus, however it remains unpublished 3 years later.

Institut Pasteur dissolved their 20-year partnership with CAS in 2023²⁵, and IPS was renamed the Shanghai Institute of Immunity and Infection.

Method

Synonymous and non-synonymous mutations

This analysis relies heavily on the ratio of synonymous to non-synonymous mutations between pairs of viruses. Unless otherwise indicated, the ratio referred to is the division of a simple count of synonymous by the count of non-synonymous mutations, not a normalized dN/dS according to the formula of Jukes and Cantor. *SNAP diagrams* are based on a Python translation of Perl code available from https://www.hiv.lanl.gov/content/sequence/SNAP/help_files/README.html. Additional code for creating heatmaps of the S/N ratio utilizes this same Perl script and is available at <https://sars2.net/scripts.html>.

The analysis firstly seeks to establish a baseline of expectations, by comparing a control group of sequences considered reliable, before considering those purporting to support a natural origin of SARS-CoV-2.

Results

Control Group

Asian sarbecovs

Because of doubts over the provenance of many Chinese sarbecovs, only the earliest to be published are shown here²⁶, along with a more recent sequence from Vietnam.

SNAP comparisons between pairs of HKU3/Rp3/Rm1 have an S:N ratio of ~4-5 for both spike and full genome, although Rf1 is somewhat more divergent. There tends to be a higher proportion of non-synonymous mutations in the NTD and RBM regions. S2 and the RBD regions flanking the RBM are better conserved. This is consistent with there being greater selection pressure from the immune system on surface exposed, and contact residues, although pressure overall is weak.

Rm1 vs Rp3

Rm1 vs Rp3

HKU3-1 vs Rp3

HKU3-1 vs Rp3

HKU3-1 vs Rf1

HKU3-1 vs Rf1

Rf1 has an interesting relationship with the Korean viruses. Most non-synonymous mutations are in the NTD of spike, but the synonymous line also has a distinct change of gradient suggesting a possible recombination.

GB Sarbecovs

Sarbecovs from Great Britain were sampled by three different groups²⁷²⁸²⁹, between 2021-22. They are all relatively close genetically with nucleotide identity >97% in the spike. Despite this the S:N ratio is generally lower than Chinese sarbecovs typically around 2. The NTD is notably more variable with an S:N ratio around 1. They were sampled from 2 species *R ferrumequinum* and *R hipposideros*.

RhGB01 vs RhGB08

Accessions: QYC92806.1, WDS46303 S: 59 N: 16 I: 0 S/N: 3.69 N/S: 0.27

RhGB02 vs RhGB05

Accessions: UZH24811.1, UZH24822 S: 49 N: 32 I: 0 S/N: 1.52 N/S: 0.66

RhGB02 vs RhGB05

Accessions: OP776338, OP776339 S: 415 N: 144 I: 0 S/N: 2.89 N/S: 0.35

RhGB01 vs RfGB02

RhGB01 vs RfGB02

RhGB04 vs RfGB02

RhGB04 and RfGB02 have the highest S/N ratio of the GB sarbecov pairs although the GenBank sequence for RhGB04 is labelled partial, unverified and missing all of ORF1ab.

African and European sarbecovs

Other than Great Britain, African and European sarbecovs unfortunately aren't well sampled, given the vast geographic area between Russia, Bulgaria, the UK and East Africa. They form a distinct lineage from Asian sarbecovs.

Khosta-2 vs RhGB01

Accessions: QVN46569, QYC92806 S: 461 N: 305 I: 5 S/N: 1.51 N/S: 0.66

Khosta-2 vs RhGB01

Accessions: MZ190138.1, MW719567 S: 2667 N: 975 I: 76 S/N: 2.74 N/S: 0.37

This geographically distant pair shows evolutionary divergence in S1, though this is markedly less in S2.

Khosta-1 vs BM48-31 spike

Accessions: QVN46559, YP_003858584 S: 556 N: 298 I: 7 S/N: 1.86 N/S: 0.54

Khosta-1 vs BM48-31

Accessions: MZ190137, NC_014470 S: 2164 N: 903 I: 32 S/N: 2.40 N/S: 0.42

This pair were collected on either side of the Black Sea, the Khosta sequences from Sochi on the eastern shore. The spike again is divergent, though more evenly across both S1 and S2. Much of ORF1ab is well conserved.

BtKY72 (Kenya) vs Khosta-1 (Russia)

Despite the vast geographical separation, there are still regions of relatively good conservation between this pair.

BB9904 vs BM48-31

Merbecovs

MERS is also suspected of being artificial, and will be the subject of a future paper. There are three main lineages whose first members were HKU4 and HKU5 from Southern China and NeoCov from Africa. The lineages aren't particularly close to each other however, so there are few pairs worth comparing. More recent sequences purporting to bridge the lineages should also be regarded as suspect.

NeoCoV vs PDF-2180

Accessions: AGY29650.2, YP_009361857

Syn:472 Non-syn:130 Indel:1 S/N:3.64 N/S:0.27 dS/dN:21.06

NeoCoV was collected in South Africa, while PDF-2180 is from Uganda, both in 2011.

21164-6 vs OV-157

Accessions: QQJ42204.1, QWO79056.1 S: 312 N: 106 I: 0 S/N: 2.96 N/S: 0.34

21164-6 vs OV-157

Accessions: MN482243, MN535733 S: 934 N: 231 I: 0 S/N: 4.04 N/S: 0.25

13585-35 vs 13585-58

Accessions: QWO79044, QWO79050 S: 40 N: 7 I: 0 S/N: 5.71 N/S: 0.17

13585-35 vs 13585-58

Accessions: MN535731, MN535732 S: 717 N: 232 I: 10 S/N: 3.09 N/S: 0.32

MOW15-21 vs MOW15-23

Accessions: WAB00011.1, WBU87226.1 S: 49 N: 28 I: 0 S/N: 1.75 N/S: 0.57

MOW15-21 vs MOW15-23

Accessions: OP919651, OQ230639 S: 278 N: 65 I: 5 S/N: 4.28 N/S: 0.23

21164-6 vs O20_16

Accessions: QQJ42204.1, QDE55565.1 S: 336 N: 210 I: 19 S/N: 1.60 N/S: 0.62

21164-6 vs O20_16

Accessions: MN482243, MG923574.2 S: 1072 N: 362 I: 21 S/N: 2.96 N/S: 0.34

Western Australian alphacoronaviruses

This set, which includes a Peruvian virus, are mostly too distant from each other to provide a useful comparison, however there is one pair at 95.3% identical shown below.

WA2028 vs WA3301

WA2028 vs WA3301

Human coronaviruses

Examples of two endemic human coronaviruses OC43 and 229E are below, though they may not be all that relevant as a comparison. The S/N is approximately 1 across the genome, although with considerable more variability in the Spike, and in the case of OC43 also the NS2 and HE genes.

The lower S/N lends some support to the hypothesis that bat immune systems may be more tolerant, and in human viruses there is more selection pressure on immunogenic regions.

OC43 (US, 2021) vs OC43 (Singapore, 2011)

Accessions: PP187318, PQ187636

Syn:82 Non-syn:66 Indel:5 S/N:1.17 N/S:0.86 dS/dN:4.69

OC43 (Tanzania, 2018) vs OC43 (Singapore, 2011)

Accessions: PQ187637, PQ187636

Syn:64 Non-syn:56 Indel:5 S/N:1.06 N/S:0.94 dS/dN:4.32

OC43 (US, 2021) vs OC43 (Canada, 2021)

Accessions: PP187318, OM386795

Syn:48 Non-syn:32 Indel:0 S/N:1.50 N/S:0.67 dS/dN:5.60

229E (US, 2023) vs 229E (Singapore, 2011)

Accessions: PQ037247.1, PQ187615.1

Syn:52 Non-syn:47 Indel:7 S/N:0.96 N/S:1.04 dS/dN:4.01

229E (US, 2023) vs 229E (US, 2016)

Accessions: PQ037247.1, KY369914

Syn:52 Non-syn:46 Indel:0 S/N:1.13 N/S:0.88 dS/dN:4.10

SARS-CoV-2 variants

Comparisons of SARS-CoV-2 variants to the earliest human sequences sampled in Wuhan illustrate very different evolutionary pressures to endemically circulating bat viruses, some have an extremely high proportion of non-synonymous mutations. There are adaptive pressures and also strong pressure from the immune system, and in later variants vaccines and monoclonal antibodies. The pressure to adapt away from Wuhan-Hu-1 is concentrated in the spike as most vaccines targeted spike only. Recently we might hypothesize that adaptive pressures have subsided somewhat, the S/N in Orf1ab is around 1 between currently circulating strains. However spike evolution still appears driven strongly by immune evasion. RBM and NTD are, as expected, the most variable domains, with the NTD tolerant of indels. The evolution of SARS-CoV-2 variants is an interesting topic in its own right, which may be explored in a future paper.

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 B.1

Accessions: NC_045512, PQ469649.1

Syn:10 Non-syn:20 Indel:3 S/N:0.40 N/S:2.47 dS/dN:1.65

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1

Accessions: NC_045512, PQ481545.1

Syn:13 Non-syn:23 Indel:62 S/N:0.15 N/S:6.54 dS/dN:2.01

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 Alpha

Accessions: NC_045512, PQ481546.1

Syn:10 Non-syn:20 Indel:128 S/N:0.06 N/S:15.63 dS/dN:1.65

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 Delta

Accessions: NC_045512.2, PQ169762.1

Syn:9 Non-syn:29 Indel:4 S/N:0.27 N/S:3.67 dS/dN:1.10

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 Omicron

Accessions: NC_045512, OP012944.1

Syn:14 Non-syn:60 Indel:14 S/N:0.18 N/S:5.44 dS/dN:0.81

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs SARS-CoV-2 XEC

Accessions: NC_045512, PQ535914.1

Syn:34 Non-syn:98 Indel:14 S/N:0.30 N/S:3.29 dS/dN:1.24

SARS-CoV-2 Omicron vs SARS-CoV-2 XEC

Accessions: OP012944, PQ535914.1

Syn:30 Non-syn:86 Indel:10 S/N:0.31 N/S:3.20 dS/dN:1.24

SARS-CoV-2 JN.1.7 vs SARS-CoV-2 XEC

Accessions: OP012944, PQ535914.1

Syn:30 Non-syn:86 Indel:10 S/N:0.31 N/S:3.20 dS/dN:1.24

SADS/SeACoV/PEAV

HKU2 (HK) vs HKU2 (GD)

Accessions: ABQ57232.1, ABQ57208.1 S: 135 N: 14 I: 0 S/N: 9.64 N/S: 0.10

HKU2 (HK) vs HKU2 (GD)

Accessions: EF203067.1, EF203064.1 S: 317 N: 87 I: 0 S/N: 3.63 N/S: 0.28

162140 vs SADS

Accessions: AVM80500, AVM80439 S: 136 N: 22 I: 1 S/N: 6.07 N/S: 0.16

162140 vs SADS

Accessions: MF094688, MF094681 S: 328 N: 74 I: 2 S/N: 4.40 N/S: 0.23

162140 vs SADS Fujian

Accessions: AVM80500, AXP98439 S: 71 N: 5 I: 0 S/N: 14.20 N/S: 0.07

162140 vs SADS Fujian

Accessions: MF094688, MH615810 S: 233 N: 54 I: 0 S/N: 4.31 N/S: 0.23

162140 vs 141388

Accessions: AVM80500, AVM80492 S: 9 N: 3 I: 0 S/N: 3.00 N/S: 0.33

162140 vs 141388

Accessions: MF094688, MF094687 S: 199 N: 100 I: 5 S/N: 1.99 N/S: 0.50

SARS-CoV-2 Related Coronaviruses

ZC45/ZXC21 and related viruses

The ZC45 viruses largely remain unpublished. There are dozens of RdRp sequences in Genbank for which no genome or spike sequences have been published. There are also sequences WIV has a

Although high, an S/N ratio of 5.28 is not exceptionally so, compared to other pairs of Chinese SARSr-Covs. Synonymous mutations are concentrated in S1, but this may be the

Comparisons between WIV's hidden ZC45-like sequences and the Zhoushan viruses are *inconsistent with natural evolution*. In this example there are 13.3 synonymous mutations to every non-synonymous. Putatively these were sampled in different bat species *R. pusillus* for ZC45 and *R. sinicus* for the Guangdong sequences. The count of total mutations at 172 is unusually low given the distance of ~1200km between bat colonies.

ZC45 Spike vs Rs8561_Guangdong

The comparison between the three spike identical viruses and the fourth Rp140346, is even more unusual with just 3 non-synonymous mutations, giving an extremely high S/N ratio of 37.7. The samples are purportedly from different bat species *R. pearsonii* and *R. sinicus*. This chart has plateaus where there are no mutations of any type, including one over the RBM. In some cases, where there are low total mutations, this might just be due to chance, though it seems unlikely here.

Rs8561_Guangdong vs Rp140346_Guangdong

Although WIV's sequences remain unpublished another group recently published a ZC45 virus found in Guangdong. This also has an unnaturally high S/N ratio of 42 compared with WIV's suppressed sequences.

GD/L102.18/2022 vs Rs8561_Guangdong

Accessions: WCZ55828, QFS22566 Syn:42 Non-syn:1 Indel:0 S/N:42.00 N/S:0.02 dS/dN:152.03

These synonymous changes make it closer to ZC45 giving it an N/S of 14. Despite a different host species (*R. affinis*) and 1200km distance, it is closer in amino acid sequence than ZC45's close neighbor ZXC21, which shares the same host species.

GD/L102.18 vs ZXC21

Accessions: WCZ55828, AVP78042 S: 146 N: 19 I: 1 S/N: 7.68 N/S: 0.13

GD/L102.18 vs ZC45

Accessions: WCZ55828, AVP78031 S: 157 N: 11 I: 0 S/N: 14.27 N/S: 0.07

Pangolin coronaviruses

The two clades of pangolin coronavirus are quite divergent, particularly in the NTD of spike, where the S/N ratio is <1.

GD pangolin (MP789) vs GX Pangolin (P2V)

Accessions: QIG55945, QVT76606

Syn:500 Non-syn:254 Indel:6 S/N:1.97 N/S:0.51 dS/dN:12.86

The reason for interest in the GD pangolin is clear when compared to SARS-CoV-2. Aside from the NTD (and the FCS insert) the S/N ratio through the rest of the spike is gene is ~ 9 , and the RBM is nearly identical.

SARS-CoV-2 vs GD pangolin (MP789)

Accessions: YP_009724390, QIG55945

Syn:407 Non-syn:195 Indel:10 S/N:2.09 N/S:0.48 dS/dN:11.29

Wuhan-Hu-1 vs GD pangolin (MP789)

Accessions: NC_045512.2, MT121216.1

Syn:2354 Non-syn:516 Indel:39 S/N:4.24 N/S:0.24 dS/dN:21.94

RaTG13

RaTG13 was for some time the closest virus to SARS-CoV-2. While the overall S/N ratio of ~ 5 would not be unusual for a pair of Chinese bat viruses, there is a leap in host species from bat to human. But most non-synonymous mutations are concentrated in the RBM. If we exclude the RBM, the S/N ratio is ~ 10 . The NTD is generally expected to be hypervariable, even with the same host species.

SARS-CoV-2 vs RaTG13

Accessions: YP_009724390, QHR63300

Syn:222 Non-syn:40 Indel:4 S/N:5.55 N/S:0.18 dS/dN:23.79

The FCS insert occurs in an otherwise extremely well conserved region from the RBM, with just 5 non-synonymous mutations. This was perhaps first noticed by Bob Garry who commented “I just can’t figure out how this gets accomplished in nature”.

A proposed reason for the lack of adaptation is that Wuhan-Hu-1 was sampled very soon after a spillover into humans, before there had been time for significant adaptation. This seems the only realistic possibility, but even if the comparison was between two bat hosted viruses, the high S/N - particularly in the NTD - is unusual.

A suggestion that was first floated by Xiao et al, 2020 was that the virus may have been formed as a recombinant resulting from the substitution of the RBM of a RaTG13-like bat virus, with one similar to a GD pangolin. This hypothetical recombinant (or artificial chimera as others have suggested) is indeed extremely close in the spike to SARS-CoV-2, though an S/N ratio of >10 seems extremely unlikely given three quite different host species are involved.

RmYN02

RmYN02 was initially of most interest for the “proto-FCS” motif at the S1|S2 junction, which resulted in much debate over whether it could be an evolutionary link to the PRRA motif of the SARS-CoV-2 FCS. Regardless, it expanded the domain of possibilities in what had previously been a well conserved motif in Chinese sarbecovs.

While RmYN02 is closer to SARS-CoV-2 than RaTG13 in much of the genome, it is not close in the spike, with 927 mutations and 54 indels. The S/N ratio is below.

The NTD of RmYN02 is highly divergent from that of ZC45, with S/N <0.5, however in the RBD the S/N is >3.

RacCS20

RacCS203 is very close in the spike to RmYN02, particularly the RBD and the 3' end of the NTD. The overall S/N ratio of 6.5 is unusually high particularly given different bat species and approximately 1000km distance between sampling sites.

African sarbecovs

The African sarbecovs published by PREDICT and UC Davis in 2021 have significantly higher S/N ratios than pairs discovered earlier. While in part this may be due to their higher overall nucleotide identity, the distribution of non-synonymous mutations is also highly unusual.

Remarkably, the lack of selection pressure seems much weaker in the spike with an S:N ratio of 5.9 compared to the full genome at 2.7.

BtKY72 (Kenya) vs PDF-2386 (Uganda)

While BtKY72 was collected in August, 2007, PDF-2386 was collected in May, 2013. Remarkably the RBM has accumulated just one amino acid substitution and one deletion after nearly 6 years evolution. Also unusual is that the region towards the 3' end of S1 is more variable than the RBD.

PRD-0038 vs PDF-2386

PRD-0038 vs PDF-2386

There is an unusual distribution of synonymous mutations between this pair, characterized by several close together, followed by a plateau.

Japanese sarbecovs

The Japanese sarbecovs don't have S/N ratios that seem out of the ordinary.

However looking at specific pairs reveals an unusual distribution of non-synonymous mutations, possibly suggestive of multiple recombination events, but at breakpoints at start of spike, end of NTD and bracketing the RBM, which are the locations most used for engineering artificial chimeras.

BANAL viruses

The Banal viruses stand out in that each of them has a high S:N ratio, in comparison to one or more sequences published earlier in 2020. Their amino acid sequences support the veracity of those sequences, while the addition of silent mutations creates some evolutionary distance.

SARS-CoV-2 vs Banal-20-52

Accessions: YP_009724390, UAY13217

Syn:176 Non-syn:20 Indel:4 S/N:9.00 N/S:0.11 dS/dN:36.83

Banal-20-52 clusters with RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2, and has an extraordinarily high S/N ratio of 9. This would be remarkable even if sampled from two bats of the same species, let alone that one is from the feces of a Laotian bat, and one from the lungs of a human. While Banal-20-52 attracted interest for supplanting RaTG13 as closest to SARS-CoV-2 in the spike, the hypothetical RaTG13/ GD Pangolin Chimera is still closer in amino acid sequence with 16 non-synonymous mutations.

The S:N ratio in the genome as a whole, at 5.6, is lower than that of the spike gene alone, implying less selection pressure on the spike than other genes.

Banal-20-52 vs Wuhan-Hu-1

Accessions: MZ937000, NC_045512.2

Syn:774 Non-syn:125 Indel:13 S/N:5.61 N/S:0.18 dS/dN:23.93

The comparison between Banal-20-52 and its close relative Banal-20-236 is suggestive of several recombination events, most obviously bracketing the NTD.

Banal-20-52 vs Banal-20-236

Accessions: UAY13217, UAY13229

Syn:163 Non-syn:166 Indel:6 S/N:0.98 N/S:1.02 dS/dN:3.83

Banal-20-52 vs Banal-20-236

Accessions: MZ937000, MZ937003

Syn:402 Non-syn:248 Indel:8 S/N:1.57 N/S:0.64 dS/dN:5.99

Banal-20-236 is particularly close to Banal-20-103 in the spike, though several possible breakpoints are evident through the genome. The NTD is noteworthy in having 26 synonymous mutations but only 1 non-synonymous, in what is usually a most variable region. This might be explained by a recent double recombination, but it is interesting that the apparent selection pressures are so different.

Banal-20-236 vs Banal-20-103

Accessions: UAY13253, UAY13229 S: 40 N: 5 I: 0 S/N: 8.00 N/S: 0.12

Banal-20-236 vs Banal-20-103

Accessions: MZ937003, MZ937001 S: 376 N: 90 I: 0 S/N: 4.20 N/S: 0.24

Banal-20-116 and Banal-20-247 are very similar with just 42 total mutations between them. Though there are perhaps not enough data points to be significant, this pair are uncommon in having more non-synonymous than synonymous mutations overall, including in the spike.

Banal-20-116 vs Banal-20-247

Banal-20-116 vs Banal-20-247

But this is not the case when comparing either to RmYn02. A striking feature of these two sequences is that the amino acid sequence is identical (or nearly) to RmYn02 over the entire RBD and flanking regions, while there are still many synonymous mutations in this region.

Banal-20-247 vs RmYn02

Banal-20-52 vs Banal-20-247

Banal-20-52 vs Banal-20-247

Banal-20-52, when compared to Banal-20-247 or Banal-20-116 has two main regions of high variability - in the NTD of spike and ORF8.

Banal-20-103 and Banal-20-236 have a very high S:N ratio when compared to the Guangdong pangolin coronaviruses. The RBM has just one amino acid change. This does not seem compatible with a host and tissue tropism switch.

Discussion

It was unfortunately difficult to construct a control group of sequences that had depth, and was sufficiently independent of Chinese state institutions, while still being genetically similar to the sequences under suspicion.

The S/N ratio is somewhat correlated to the nucleotide % identity.

For extremely close (>99.8% identity) viruses the S/N can be distorted (in either direction) by a handful of mutations. These outliers should be excluded.

For closely related (>90% identity) viruses a typical S/N is in the order of 2-4

Conclusions

The provenance of SARS-CoV-2 related coronaviruses is murky. Not a single example was known before 2018, despite 15 years of searching for SARS-like viruses. New sequences piled up rapidly following the pandemic, initially coming from WIV, AMMS, and AMMS-linked sources. Several international groups later contributed, although many of these have close ties to WIV and/or AMMS. Institut Pasteur is a source with high reputation, and great weight has been given to its evidence, particularly the “Banal” sequences. However it too has a long and close collaboration with AMMS, WIV and CAS, and links extend to the upper echelons of French and Chinese politics.

Some bizarre incidents and circumstances surround the scientific exploration of SARS-CoV-2 origins:

- WIV sequences have been kept secret on Genbank for years despite relevance to their publications
- WIV's sequence database was taken offline in September 2019, and never restored
- Pangolin sequence data wasn't published four months after the first paper referencing it
- the same pangolin sequence data was used by multiple groups, sometimes without disclosure
- Chinese military authors appear on many papers, and have supplied data and samples to others
- Even several of the foreign groups have Chinese military links
- There is evidence of novel viruses being cloned secretly, and sequence data not published
- WIV submitted two papers in one day with different conclusions, didn't disclose existence of data
- Institut Pasteur embarked on a new sampling expedition despite having 500 samples in storage, which still haven't been sequenced

Beyond this, my previous work has showed the likelihood of fraud with respect to the evidence of SARS-1 being of natural origin. WIV and AMMS were also central to that fraud.

But even discounting this, and other much discussed controversies (such as the Furin Cleavage Site) there is little consistency in the evolutionary trail and plenty to suggest that more data may be fraudulent.

There are many SARS-CoV-2 sequences where there are an abnormally high proportion of synonymous mutations. Although it may be that differences in bat immune system account for some of this, and we should perhaps not expect similar in human viruses, we should wonder why these viruses are evolving differently. A possible explanation from the perspective of an artificial origin, is that synonymous mutations

Why is there so little apparent pressure on the RBM? It has been suggested that perhaps the RBM has evolved to an "optimal state" where it is adapted equally well to bat, pangolins and human. But we see that once in the human population the RBM is the focus of greatest pressure to adapt. This is also observed between most pairs of (non SARS-CoV-2 related) bat viruses, even where the spike is well-adapted and stable with a high proportion of synonymous mutations. The RBM and NTD are the most immune exposed regions of the genome, and we should expect relatively stronger pressure there, even if overall it is weak.

And is there for some reason was weak pressure to adapt in the RBM, why are their dramatic exceptions to this – such as RaTG13, where the majority of non-synonymous mutations are in this one region?

Recombination is sometimes offered as a reason why some sequences might have low homology in the RBM or NTD, but high homology elsewhere, but this contradicts the idea that such a domain might evolve to some optimal state where pressure to adapt becomes extremely low.

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